

Can water-soluble vitamins be over-dosed? Research on vitamin C

[Darf man wasserlösliche Vitamine überdosieren? Versuche mit Vitamin C]

GORDONOFF T. [Can water-soluble vitamins be over-dosed? Research on vitamin C].

Schweiz Med Wochenschr. 1960 Jul 2;90:726-9. German. PMID: 13851245.

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This is an English translation of the main sections of a study with 19 guinea pigs by Gordonoff. The current relevance of this paper arises from the findings of the LOVIT trial with sepsis patients [1] and of a study on COVID-19 patients [2].

Sudden termination of high-dose vitamin C in humans has been shown to cause a decrease in vitamin C concentrations to levels lower than those recorded before the high-dose administration [3-6]. This is known as the rebound effect. In some circumstances, the abrupt termination of high-dose vitamin C may substantially decrease plasma levels leading to harmful effects.

We previously showed that the sudden termination of 4-day intravenous vitamin C in the LOVIT trial explained the harm observed in the participants who had been randomized to the vitamin C group [1,7]. Patients in the vitamin C group were administered vitamin C after randomization with a dose of 50 mg/kg body weight every 6 hours (16 g/day for an 80 kg person). There was no difference in survival between the groups in the trial during the 4-day vitamin C administration. However, during days 5 to 7 mortality was significantly elevated in the vitamin C group with RR= 2.28 (95% CI: 1.24–4.2; vitamin C 33 vs. placebo 15 deaths) [7]. After the clear increase in mortality immediately after vitamin C was terminated, the difference in survival curves leveled off [1,7]. This pattern is consistent with the notion of the rebound effect being the cause of the short-term difference in mortality between the LOVIT trial groups.

In the recent COVID-19 study, two prospectively harmonized randomized clinical trials enrolled critically ill patients receiving organ support in ICU and patients who were not critically ill [2]. Both studies examined the same vitamin C protocol as the LOVIT trial: 4-day intravenous vitamin C with a dose of 50 mg/kg every 6 hours. The results of the two separate COVID-19 trials were pooled at the end, with 1493 patients assigned to vitamin C and 1097 assigned to the control group. In the critically ill COVID-19 patients, there was no difference in mortality during vitamin C administration, but there was a significant increase in mortality in the vitamin C group immediately after the termination of vitamin C [2,8]. This harm after the termination of high-dose vitamin C is also consistent with the rebound effect [8].

The guinea pig study by Gordonoff indicates that the rebound effect can lead to increased mortality in certain contexts. Nine guinea pigs were administered 0.5 g/day vitamin C subcutaneously for 4 weeks. After termination of the high dose vitamin C the guinea pigs were fed a scurvy diet and they died on average after 25 days. Control animals that were fed a scurvy diet with no high dose vitamin C beforehand died on average after 39 days, with $P = 0.000\ 000\ 07$ for the difference in the t-test. This guinea pig study supports the interpretation that the increased mortality after abrupt termination of high-dose vitamin C in the LOVIT trial and the study with COVID-19 patients is explained by the rebound effect [1,2,7,8].

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Can water-soluble vitamins be over-dosed? Research on vitamin C

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Swiss Medical Weekly 1960 No. 27 pp.726-729.

Von T. Gordonoff, Bern

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Author's summary:

Summary. Guinea pigs who have received very large doses of vitamin C previous to a scurvy diet will fall prey to, and die earlier of scurvy than those having previously received physiologic amounts of vitamin C. The studies of vitamin C elimination in those animals who have received vitamin C show that as soon as they are placed on a scurvy diet, the excretion of vitamin C is greatly reduced. It appears that there is a vitamin C regulating mechanism. It is therefore not recommended to administer large doses (grams per day), over a long period of time.

On the following pages is the translation of the relevant parts of the paper.

At the end is the full German version of the text.

This appears to be a related report:

GORDONOFF T. [On abusive vitaminotherapy. Trials with vitamin C].

Therapie. 1960;15:623-8. French. PMID: 13707208.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13707208>

With his prophetic statement that unknown substances, that are necessary for life, must be present in our food, even in the smallest quantities, *Hopkins (1906)*¹ had set science two tasks: *to identify these unknown substances*, and *to determine the quantities necessary* for humans and animals.

The first task was solved fairly quickly. These unknown substances were soon isolated, some of them already synthesized, and they now play an important role in therapy as *vitamins*.

...

On the other hand, the second question about the amounts of the individual vitamins needed has not yet been fully resolved. When administering cod liver oil it has not, for understandable reasons, been possible to supply large quantities of the vitamins A and D contained in it. But when the first vitamin A concentrate came on the market, it was soon seen that hypervitaminotic disorders occur with overdoses, and the same was also the case when vitamin D was isolated.

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The problem is more difficult with the *water-soluble vitamins*. They are all considered to be non-toxic, so there is no upper limit set to their quantities: the excess quantities are excreted with the urine. It is therefore also easy to overdose because the optimal requirement for the water-soluble vitamins is not a known quantity.

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Recently, vitamins have no longer been playing the role of accessory nutrients; they are often also administered due to their other pharmacodynamic properties, and in all these cases it is easy to overdose.

If, in such special cases, the vitamins are administered *temporarily* at higher doses, there is no objection to that because the therapeutic range of the water-soluble vitamins really is very wide.

...

Quantities of from 30 mg to a maximum of 75 mg of vitamin C per day are sufficient. Vitamin C is currently available on the market in doses of 1 g each, and these amounts are taken by completely healthy individuals, stimulated by advertising, several times a day.

1 Hopkins FG. *Analyst* **31**, 386 (1906) <https://doi.org/10.1039/AN906310385B> ; <https://ia800708.us.archive.org>
J. Physiol. (Lond.) **44**, 425 (1912) <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1912.sp001524> ;
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1512834>

If you follow the literature on vitamins, you can see that the water-soluble vitamins cannot be said to be completely harmless. More or less toxic effects have been observed with any vitamin when taken in excess doses. I mention here folic acid which, when administered for a long time, leads to the flushing out of riboflavin and depletion of the body's stores of vitamin B₁₂, making the symptoms worse. Dyspeptic conditions have been observed with the administration of high doses of vitamin C, with greater agitation and insomnia. *Roch* warns against high doses of vitamin C as they can cause headaches, nausea and diarrhoea in adults. *Roch* recommends administering vitamin C only in the morning and at midday, and not in the evening, because it can lead to insomnia. These unpleasant side effects, which could also be described as hypervitaminoses, are by no means serious as they disappear when the dose is reduced and especially when the medication is stopped.

In our analysis we are not thinking of the vitamins that, under certain circumstances, doctors may administer in higher doses as well; we would like to look at the vitamins that people buy themselves in pharmacies and drugstores and with which they become oversaturated.

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Every tissue and every cell contains vitamins, and vitamin C in particular is an intermediate acceptor in the course of oxidation and dehydration processes. The first symptom of vitamin C deficiency is a decrease in serum phosphatase. In scorbutic guinea pigs, the activity of liver esterase, liver phosphatase and respiratory enzymes is reduced. Vitamin C activates thrombin and stimulates blood platelet formation. Ascorbic acid is necessary for the formation of collagen. According to *Wachholder* and *Podestà*, vitamin C is stored in the adrenal glands, the liver, the anterior lobe of the pituitary gland, the corpus luteum and the placenta. The adrenal cortex and both the gonads contain a good deal of vitamin C, and it is precisely in these organs that steroid hormones are produced. *Kersten, Kersten* and *Staudinger* assume that ascorbic acid is involved in the formation of steroid hormones.

With so many functions that make vitamin C essential to metabolism, the body must be able to store vitamin C and regulate its metabolism. Even in the case of manifest scurvy, the organs are not completely free of vitamin C.

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In any case it is justified to assume that when the body is constantly oversaturated with any vitamin, the protective and regulatory mechanisms are switched off.

Following on from this theory, we treated a series of 10 guinea pigs, each with 0.5 g of vitamin C subcutaneously daily. The animals received the same diet as their sister animals of the same age. After 4 weeks, the two series, those which had been previously treated with vitamin C as well as the sister animals, were put on a scurvy diet. For this we used the feed mix from the Lister Institute, in the *Matmon* modification.

The results of our investigations are shown in **Figure 1**.

Here we see the lifespan of the scorbutic guinea pigs²; on the left the animals previously fed with the institute's usual feed mixture, which contains 500 mg/kg of vitamin C, were fed normally and then put on a scurvy diet. On the right, the animals received the same diet, but for 4 weeks previously were oversaturated with 0.5 g of vitamin C subcutaneously per animal per day. While the average lifespan of the guinea pigs without pretreatment with vitamin C was 38.6 days, the guinea pigs after pretreatment with vitamin C died on average after 24.88 days. The difference is very clear (significance to the confidence threshold of 1% [i.e. $P < 0.01$]).³

Uehlinger characterizes the degrees of scurvy as follows: inhibition of bone formation +, inhibition of bone formation and bleeding ++, complete picture with fracture + + +. In the pretreated animals, 3 had the degree of + + + and 6 the degree of +. In the non-pretreated animals, the degree + + + was also reached in 3 guinea pigs and degree + in 4 animals; in 3 guinea pigs, however, the findings were normal. The clinical picture was also in line with the findings, as the pretreated animals appeared more severely affected with the disease.

We also investigated the elimination ratios in the guinea pigs using the *Roe* and *Kuether* method. In **Figure 2** it can be seen that with the animals pretreated with vitamin C, as soon as they are put on a scurvy diet, the elimination of vitamin C stops on the very next day, while animals that are fed normally do not need to protect themselves against the loss of vitamin C and therefore eliminate greater amounts of vitamin C.

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2 With thanks to the company Hoffmann-La Roche & Cie AG in Basel for providing the ascorbic acid and the guinea pigs.

3 HH: t-test calculation of the data in Figure 1 gives $P = 0.000\ 000\ 07$. See page 8.

Based on our studies with vitamin C, we believe that it can be assumed that there is no justification for administering excessive doses of a single vitamin, in this case vitamin C, over a lengthy period of time. If, for some reason, a greater need for vitamin C arises – this could be the case with infectious diseases, during pregnancy and lactation, and also with greater muscular activity, such as for example with sportspeople when they are training – in a case like this the body is in a worse position than a body on a normal diet.

In our opinion, in view of the suggestions to administer individual vitamins in excessively high doses, it is important to raise the question for discussion from this point of view. The question could also be asked as to whether it is justified to recommend vitamins in large doses to aging individuals over a lengthy period of time. Of course, the elderly person absorbs vitamins from food less well, but this person's requirement is also less than that of young individuals.

In any event we have demonstrated that patients *who have been given doses of vitamin C that are too high are in a worse position if, for any reason, a vitamin C deficiency were to occur than those who eat normally.*

Figure 1. The lifespan of guinea pigs which, previously on a normal diet, were put on a scurvy diet. The black column shows the average lifespan of all animals (38.6 days). — On the right, the animals were fed the same but received 0.5 g of ascorbic acid per animal per day every day for 4 weeks. The black column shows the average lifespan of the laboratory animals (24.88 days) after they had been put on a scurvy diet.

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Abb. 1. Links die Lebensdauer der Meerschweinchen, die, früher normal

HH: Calculation with R:

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> t.test(Days ~ DoseC, data= Gordonoff, var.equal=T)
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Two Sample t-test

data: Days by DoseC

t = -9, df = 17, p-value = 7e-08

alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group high and group normal is not equal to 0

95 percent confidence interval:

-16.93 -10.49

sample estimates:

mean in group high mean in group normal

24.89 38.60

Figure 2. The elimination of ascorbic acid after 14 days of pretreatment with 0.5 g of ascorbic acid per animal per day. As soon as the animals are put on a scurvy diet, they stop excreting vitamin C. The figures above the columns indicate the amounts of vitamin C excreted in mg.

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Abb. 2. Links die Elimination der Ascorbinsäure nach 14tägiger Vorbehandlung mit je 0.5 g Ascorbinsäure pro Tier und Tag. Rechts die Elimination der Ascorbinsäure nach 5tägiger Vorbehandlung mit je 0.5 g Ascorbinsäure pro Tier und Tag.